

OBTAINING SENSITIVE MATERIALS THAT SENSE LIGHT AND TEMPERATURE

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ABSTRACT

Mechanical treatment (cutting, physical and chemical cleaning, polishing) of semiconductor Si-based material, introduction of Mn(Manganese) atoms through diffusion, formation of nanoclusters of various sizes and thus light and obtaining a sensitive material that senses temperature. Nanoclusters are materials in the transition from atomic properties to bulk material properties. Since it is possible to create new properties by obtaining nanoclusters of different sizes, by alloying Mn(Manganese) atoms to the Si-based material at different temperatures, forming nanoclusters of different sizes, and studying their electrophysical parameters, light and temperature sensors is created

Keywords Light sensors, temperature sensors, nanoclusters, compensated silicon.

Performance of the subject: Current diary is taken from wide range of light and temperature. The scope of their application is constantly expanding. There are problems such as correcting sensitive materials, determining the acquisition of technology, correcting the cost. Due to the sensitivity of these materials to infrared rays, they are used in the manufacture of various electronic devices. From infrared photodetectors to remote control devices, tomographs in medicine to measure temperature and diagnose diseases, to night vision

equipment to study and control the content of solar energy, in addition to fire and control of various objects. can be done effectively.

The purpose of the research: to obtain materials sensitive to light and temperature by the diffusion method on the basis of compensated silicon and to study their sensitivity to infrared rays.

Tasks of the study: 1. Mechanical processing of semiconductor Si-based material (cutting, physical and chemical cleaning, polishing);

2. Diffusion of Mn atoms into the KDB-3 element;

3. Calculation of electrophysical parameters of samples sensitive to light and temperature as a result of diffusion;

4. To study the sensitivity of materials to infrared rays

Problem: The main concern in obtaining light- and temperature-sensitive materials is to increase their sensitivity to infrared light. The ability to perceive low-power infrared rays depends on the diffusion process. It depends on the temperature range of 1030÷1050 °C, the cooling rate of the capsule and the concentration of Mn atoms. That is, it is important to keep the same temperature, the degree to which the air is absorbed by the capsule, and the cooling rate of the capsule in exact values.

The solution to the problem: a material based on the semiconductor Si is selected and after mechanical processing, pure metal manganese, whose mass is determined in relation to the volume of the quartz ampoule, and the studied samples, into the quartz ampoule, the air inside of which is sucked (the pressure in the ampoule is 10^{-6} mm. above the wire), the ampoule is placed in the SOUL-4 diffusion furnace at room temperature ($T=300$ K). The temperature of the previously studied diffusion furnace, along with the temperature of the quartz ampoule placed inside it, is raised step by step at a rate of 5 degrees/minute. After the samples reach the temperature $T=550\div700$ °C, the samples are kept at the same temperature for $t=10\div20$ minutes. The temperature of the diffusion furnace

rises to the temperature $T=1030\div 1050$ °C at a speed of $150\div 200$ °C/min. At the same temperature, the samples are kept for $t=5\div 10$ minutes, then the quartz ampoule containing the samples is cooled by throwing them into special oil at a speed of 200 °C/second from the diffusion furnace (the safety oil used for rapid cooling of heated objects is a high-quality raw material). Then the obtained new material was ground (polished) and the oxide layer (SiO_2) was removed. The sensitivity of the new material to light and temperature was studied and its electrophysical parameters were calculated. Based on them, new types of IR sensors were made. IR sensors were made on the basis of samples of nanocluster silicon with a surface of $S=0.5$ cm², a thickness of 0.15 cm, and they were installed in a hermetic case with a glass hole.

IR sensors mounted in a silicon-based hermetic housing with multi-charged nanoclusters of manganese atoms

The results of this study show that, from all calculations, the laws established for the diffusion coefficient and solubility of manganese in silicon do not work under low temperature diffusion conditions. The solubility of manganese in silicon at the given temperature $T=550\div 700$ °C is $N_{\text{Mn}}\sim 10^{10}$ cm⁻³, the diffusion coefficient is $D=2\cdot 10^{-8}\div 5\cdot 10^{-8}$ cm²/s, in which samples with a thickness of 1 mm for the same alloying $t = \frac{l^2}{4\cdot D} = \frac{0,1^2}{4\cdot 2\cdot 10^{-8}} = 10^5$, it takes about a second, i.e. $t=3$ hours. Our new technology requires a total of 3 hours for the diffusion process. The concentration of manganese atoms in the volume is $N_{\text{Mn}}\sim (2\div 3)\cdot 10^{15}$ cm⁻³, which is 5 orders of

magnitude higher than expected. Based on the obtained results, it can be confirmed that in the low-temperature region, diffusion occurs between the nodes, and the entry atoms are located between the nodes. Additional evidence is that the concentration of vacancies in low-temperature diffusion is $N_V \sim 10^7 \text{ cm}^{-3}$, that is, it is $10^7 \div 10^8$ degrees smaller than the concentration of manganese between the nodes. The vacancy concentration is calculated using the $N = N_s \exp\left(-\frac{3}{kT}\right)$ formula.

References

1. Sharobiddinov , S., & Mamarasulov, Q. (2023). QUYOSH HAVO ISITISH KOLLEKTORINI ENERGIYA SAMARADORLIGINI OSHIRISH. Interpretation and Researches, 1(8). извлечено от <http://interpretationandresearches.uz/index.php/iar/article/view/538>
2. Zuhritdinov, A., & Xakimov, T. (2023). STUDY OF TEMPERATURE DEPENDENCE OF LINEAR EXPANSION COEFFICIENT OF SOLID BODIES. International Bulletin of Applied Science and Technology, 3(5), 888-893.
3. Olimov, L. O., & Anarboyev, I. I. (2022). Some electrophysical properties of polycrystalline silicon obtained in a solar oven. Silicon, 14(8), 3817-3822.
4. Olimov, L. O., & Anarboev, I. I. (2021). Microstructure of polycrystal silicon heated by sunlight. International Journal of Multicultural and Multireligious Understanding Ra Journal of Applied Research/rajar, 2669-2671.
5. Olimov, L. O., & Anarboev, I. I. (2021). Electrophysical properties of two structured polycrystal silicon. Theoretical & applied sciences. International journal of multidisciplinary research and analysis./ijmra, v4-i11.

6. Olimov, L. O., Anarboyev, I. I., & Davronov, A. A. (2023). ZAMONAVIY AVTOMOBILSOZLIKNING DOLZARB MUAMMOLARINI HAL ETISHDA YARIMO ‘TKAZGICHLI MATERIALKLARNI QO ‘LLANILISHI.
7. Mamirov, A. M., Anarboyev, I. I., & Yusupov, A. X. Yuqori temperaturalarga mo‘ljallangan quyosh pechi qurilmasi konstruksiyasi. Ўзбекистон Республикаси Олий ва Ўрта Махсус Таълим Вазирлиги Наманган Муҳандислик-Технология Инститuti Илмий-Техника Журнали.
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